

CRISPR/CAS9: HISTORY AND COMPONENTS, MECHANISM, APPLICATION

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ABSTRACT

CRISPR/Cas9 (Clustered Regularly Interspaced Short Palindromic Repeats) is a precise tool in gene editing that has revolutionized in life science, medicine and drug delivery. It was discovered in the 18th century as an astonishing sequence in bacteria and archaea, which developed adaptive immunity through the incorporation of spacers from foreign nucleic acids to combat invading viruses. Two women, Emmanuelle Charpentier and Jennifer Doudna, who significantly advanced the field of genetic manipulation, were awarded the Noble Prize in 2020 for their biochemical studies on CRISPR/Cas9. The basic mechanism of CRISPR involves recognition, cleavage, and repair of DNA. This process is achieved through insertion, deletion, or single base changes. CRISPR's evolutionary advancements in molecular biology have increased its therapeutic potential due to its high efficiency and effectiveness, earning it name "Genetic Scissors". It plays a crucial role in gene therapy, gene editing and the treatment to

genetic diseases. CRISPR has tremendous applications in medicine, including treating cystic fibrosis, sickle cell anemia, cancer and Duchenne Muscular Dystrophy. Although CRISPR has shown immense potential across various sectors, many applications remain disapproved due to challenges like immunogenicity of Cas9 protein, off- target effects and the risk of cancer. The review discussed the History, mechanism of action and therapeutic uses of CRISPR/Cas9.

KEYWORDS: CRISPR/Cas9, sgRNA, Genetic Scissors, off- target effects.

HISTORY & COMPONENTS

The most indispensable genome editing tool is CRISPR/Cas9 which have the application in medical, biotechnological research etc... and it will recognise, cleave, Repair the damaged or mutated DNA strand.^[1] CRISPR- Clustered Regularly Interspaced Short Palindromic Repeats, were first discovered by Ishino et al. in 1987, the different sequence present in between the IAP gene in E. coli. They identified the 29nt (nucleotide) similar sequence were arranged as repeats which is separated by 32nt unique sequence as spacer but they didn't know the biological function of these sequence.^[2] Then CRISPR (Clustered Regularly Interspaced Short Palindromic Repeats) was named by Francisco Mojica in 1990 but its function had not yet elucidated.^[1] Some researchers discover the CRISPR in prokaryotes which is an adaptive immunity for Bacteria and Archaea in 2005.^[3] The CRISPR sequence was found 40% in bacteria and 90% in archaea. This CRISPR sequence mainly composed of leader, repeats and spacers.^[4] CRISPR was an adaptive immunity for prokaryotes was experimentally proved in 2007.^[5] Unlike eukaryotic immune system, the prokaryotic immune system was somewhat different for each and every cell which contains the spacers array separated by the palindromic repeats So, this was significantly named as CRISPR array which was composed of 17-84bp of spacer.^[6] Spacer- Foreign genetic element which is from viral DNA or plasmid DNA.^[5] This sequence is separated by 25-50bp of palindromic repeats.^[7] Repeats- the repeated genetic code of the host cell which may be bacteria or archaea.^[8] In 2008, Broun's et.al were found that the array contains RNA sequence which is CRISPR- RNA (cr-RNA) that transcribed from CRISPR. The maturation process of cr- RNA by Transactivating CRISPR- RNA (Tracr- RNA) was demonstrated by Deltecheara et. al in 2011.^[3] In CRISPR/Cas9 system, tracr- RNA and cr- RNA which is replaced as single guide RNA (sgRNA) in S. pyogene.^[9] When the mature cr- RNA is complementary base paired with tracr- RNA to forms the bifunctional compound and becomes the double stranded RNA^[6] this guides the Cas9 protein and significantly make the Double stranded DNA break at specific DNA sequence which introduce the genetic modification in eukaryotic cells.^[10] In 2013, Cong and Moli et.al utilise the Cas9 protein from type II system of CRISPR for genome modification in mammalian cells.^[3] By introducing the mutation in the Cas9 domains which results in the dead Cas9. It lacks the nuclease activity but the binding activity towards the target DNA is not affected.^[11] To activate or inhibit the specific target gene by the fusion of dCas9 with the CRISPR activation or CRISPR interferons.^[3,11] Finally, the biochemical

studies demonstrated that the Double Stranded Break (DSB) in target DNA was created by Cas9 which is published in 2012 by Emmanuelle Charpentier and Jennifer Doudna and also, they were awarded Nobel Prize in chemistry for their biochemical discovery.^[10, 16] Before the discovery of CRISPR/Cas9 genome editing tool, there was some genome editing tools are available that are Cre/ loxP, Zinc Finger Nuclease (ZFN), Transcription Activator Like Effector Nuclease (TALEN). Evolution of ZFN technique was came in the late 1990s, when the researchers fuse the engineered Zinc Finger Protein (ZFP) with restriction enzyme Fok 1 to produce the ZFN. Then this ZFN capable for recognising and binds to the specific sequence of target DNA which induces the DSB in DNA strand.^[15] In the 2010, researchers were discovered the Transcription Activator Like Effector from the plant pathogen *Xanthomonas* bacterium. The fusion of engineered Transcription Activator Like Effector with the non-specific restriction endonuclease Fok 1 to produce the TALEN which recognize and binds to the target site of DNA and facilitates the DSB in target site followed by Non homologous end joining (NHEJ) or Homologous direct repair (HDR).^[16] Due to some limitations such as time consuming, low efficiency, specificity restriction, expensive, difficult designing of multiple protein for each new targets.^[17,18] Now CRISPR/Cas9 surmounted all these limitation and challenges so, CRISPR/Cas9 was the precise, less expensive genome editing technology compared to above technology.

Components of CRISPR/Cas9 system

The basic and major components of CRISPR system are cr- RNA, tracr- RNA, sg RNA and Cas protein. The cr- RNA, tracr- RNA, sg RNA is already mentioned in the history. The most important component is Cas protein which is known as CRISPR associated protein that are classified into 2 class, 6 types, 33 subtypes.^[12] In class 1 which are multi subunit effector complex and class 2 are the large single subunit effector complex.^[13]

[12, 13, 14, 11, 6]

BASIC STRUCTURE AND MACHNISM OF CRISPR/Cas9

Basic Structure of CRISPR/Cas9

The CRISPR/Cas9 system consist of tracr-RNA, cr-RNA, Cas gene, leader sequence, spacer. The CRISPR/Cas9 system was divided into 6 types and many subtypes based on the function but most commonly and widely used system was type II, the Cas9 from *S. pyogene* (SF370) which is very simple compared to others, because the protein Cas9 (~ 160kD) is the multidomain and cross- functional protein which is consist of Recognition (REC) lobe contains the long alpha helix and two REC domains such as REC1, REC2 and Nuclease (NUC) lobe contains the PAM interacting domain (PI), Ruv C domain- assist to non- target strand cleavage and HNH domain- cleaves the target strand. The another most predominant component was PAM sequence, a short 2-6bp DNA sequence which is present besides to protospacer in the invader nucleic acid.^[17,19]

Mechanism of CRISPR/Cas9 in Bacteria

The adaptive immunity of bacteria and archaea provide the self-Défense against various invader MGE which is arise from virus, bacteriophage or plasmid through three major stages that are adaptation or integration, cr RNA biogenesis or expression, interference.

Adaptation or Integration

In the CRISPR/Cas9 system, the Cas1 & Cas2, Csn2, Cas9, tracr-RNA and PAM sequence are essential for spacer accession.^[20] Due to the presence of PAM interaction domain in Cas9 which helps to recognize the PAM sequence (5'-NGG-3'), when the bacterial immune system identifies the invader nucleic acid. This PAM sequence is very important to recognize the protospacer for spacer addition. After the cleavage of 20nt protospacer by Cas9 protein retains the Cas1, 2 & Csn2 which forms the complex for integration of protospacer as spacer in between the leader and repeat sequence.^[21,22] This process will make the memorization of bacterial immunity.

Expression or cr RNA biogenesis

In the cr RNA biogenesis, the newly added spacer was transcribed from the CRISPR array into pre cr-RNA which contains repeats, spacer and the pre cr-RNA was further processed by anti- repeat sequence of tracr-RNA base paired with pre cr-RNA repeats which forms the RNA duplex and then finally the RNA duplex is matured by host Ribonuclease III (RNase III). Now the cr-RNA: tracr- RNA which is also known as sg RNA undergoes some trimming process, this decreases the length of sgRNA sequence at about 20nt resulting as mature cr-

RNA followed by interference.^[21, 23, 24]

Interference

Ribonucleoprotein complex (RNP) formation was occur when the mature sgRNA interact with Cas9 protein and the Cas9 undergoes some conformational changes to activate itself which is important for RNA guided DNA cleavage. The RNA complex cleaves the invader MGE element to create the DSB. This is achieved by REC lobe and NEC lobe.^[20, 25]

Mechanism of CRISPR/Cas9 in Genome Editing

The natural adaptive immune system of bacteria and archaea exploited the precise genome editing^[24] through the programmable sgRNA and the nuclease activity of Cas9. The gene editing was divided into 3 steps that are recognition, cleavage and repair.

Recognition and Cleavage

The programmable sgRNA consist of 5' cr-RNA and 3' tracr-RNA. The 5' cr-RNA of sgRNA contains the 20nt sequence complementary to specific target sequence which is used to identify the target DNA for gene editing to create the DSB.^[2] Now, the designed sgRNA strongly binds with the Cas9 through the generation of positive charge on their surface.^[19] This resulting the formation of RNP complex. Now, the PI domain of Cas9 recognize and binds to the PAM sequence which is present at the downstream of non- target strand of DNA.^[26] The presence of Arginine- rich motif in Cas9 mediate this recognition^[27] and the target DNA sequence complementarily binds to the sgRNA which leads to the formation of heteroduplex.^[26] The nuclease domain within Cas9 holds the target strand and the Cas9 undergoes some conformation changes for ability to cleave the target DNA. The HNH and Ruv C domain cleaves the both target and non- target strand of DNA to produce the DSB. (Fig. 1)

Figure 1.

Repair of Double Strand break

DNA undergoes the several cellular repair mechanisms after the DSB occurred. There are two major pathways available that are HDR and NHEJ. Both of them have specific repair factor for CRISPR/Cas9 mediated DSB.

Homologous Direct Repair pathway (HDR)

It is the accurate way to repair the DSB by the requirement of exogenous or endogenous donor template. This pathway only active in S/ G2 phase which is one of the major limitations. The DSB was first recognized by protein MRN complex comprise of Mre 1, Rad 50, Nbs 1 (MRN). Then the MRN complex actuate the Ataxia telangiectasis mutated (ATM) protein kinase which phosphorylate the C- terminal binding protein interacting protein (Ct1P) then the Ct1P integrate with breast cancer associated protein 1 (BRCA1) to form BRCA1/MRN/Ct1P complex this removes the 5' end of DSB to form 3' ssDNA overhangs. After this process, the replication protein A (RPA) recognize and binds to the end of the overhangs then the RPA was replaced by RAD 51 which interact with BRCA 2 to form presynaptic nucleoprotein filament complex on the ssDNA this promote the searching of endogenous or exogenous donor template for repair. Now, the intermediate displacement loop (D loop) is formed when homologous donor template invades by one of 3'ssDNA overhangs and the new DNA strand is synthesised when it recruits the DNA polymerase δ finally this was followed by either DSB repair or synthesis dependent strand annealing (SDSA) pathway.^[28,29]

Fig (2).

Homologous Direct Repair

Figure 2.

Non-Homologous End Joining (NHEJ)

NHEJ pathway is occurred first before the HDR so it is known as default repair pathway. This pathway active throughout the cell cycle. The NHEJ was commence by the recognition and binding of heterodimer which is consist of ku70 & ku80 protein at the site of DSB end. The protein binding helps to protect the DSB DNA from resection and then the formation of DNA-Pkcs (DNA Dependent protein kinase catalytic subunit) and ku protein complex was occurred when the ku protein recruit catalytic subunit of DNA-Pk. The assembly of DNA-Pk stimulates the kinase activity and directs the NHEJ pathway. Now, the nuclease Artemis is phosphorylated by DNA- Pkcs, XRCC4 (X- ray repair cross complementing protein 4), DNA ligase IV and their factors. This process promotes the joining of DNA through the assessment of polymerase μ and λ the end processing was done by the ligation enzyme which is called DNA ligase IV. Finally, the XRCC4 & DNA ligase IV perform the end joining process by gap filling or ligation which also produce the random indels at the site. So, the NHEJ is error prone editing.^[30, 31] Fig (3).

Non- Homologous End Joining

Figure 3.

Application of CRISPR/Cas9 in Genetic Diseases

The astounding advancement of CRISPR/Csa9 technology made more versatile, effective and precise tool to edit genome. CRISPR/Cas9 tool was widely used in many genetic diseases some of them are listed below that are Sickle Cell Disease, Duchenne Muscular Dystrophy, Cystic Fibrosis and other cancer treatments.^[41]

Sickle Cell Disease (SCD)

SCD is the Patrimonial blood disorder occurred through single nucleotide replacement^[32] when the adenine replaced by thymine leads to the substitution of hydrophilic glutamic acid with hydrophobic valine at the 6th position of beta – globin chain on chromosome 11^[33]

which leads to the production of abnormal haemoglobin (Hbs). Under the hypoxic condition, the Hbs forms long and rigid polymers within the RBCs through the process of polymerization resulting in the misshaping of RBC as sickle shaped.^[32] This sickle RBCs cause the event of Sever pain known as Vaso- occlusive Cries (VOCs), chronic haemolytic anemia, organ damage.^[32] SCD affected patients doesn't survive after the age of 43.^[33] In 2013, the US centre for disease control and prevention (CDC) estimate ~ 100000 Americans, 1 in 365 African and overall 3 million individuals are affected by SCD in worldwide.^[34] There are some treatments available for SCD that are blood transfusion, bone marrow transplantation this treatment only acceptable for 18% of SCD patients in US because it involves in finding healthy donor and also associated with transplant related mortality risks.^[35,36] To surmounted this limitation by utilizing the need of gene therapy for induce the expression of HbF (Foetal Haemoglobin) which restores the normal function of HBB by genome editing. During human development, the hematopoietic stem cells (HSC) are completely rearranged and located to the bone marrow from Early embryonic yolk sac which result in the transformation of HbF to adult haemoglobin (HbA) now the HBD (δ globin) and HBB (β globin) were expressed.^[34] On 16th Nov 2023, the Medicines and Healthcare products Regulatory Agency (MHRA) approved Casgevy, the 1st drug is used to treat SCD mediated by CRISPR/ Cas9 genome editing tool in patients of 12 years and above (≥ 12). On 8th Dec 2023, the US Food and Drug Administration (FDA) approves Casgevy for SCD patients and on 15th Dec 2023, the European Medicine Agency (EMA) approved Casgevy for SCD.^[34]

The aim is to achieve the disruption or deletion of BCL11A (B cell leukaemia/ lymphoma 11A) enhancer in γ – globin gene and this was also designed to retain the ability to BCL11A support HSC function.^[38] The treatment involved in the collection of CD34+ HSPCs (hematopoietic stem and pluripotent cells) from the patient's blood stream these are electroporated with Cas9 nuclease and SPY- 101 (sgRNA) which is complementary to GATA1 which is specifically binds to the enhancer region of transcription repressor BCL11A site. This binding site is present at 115bp upstream (-115) of HBG promoter.^[39] The erythroid specific enhancer region of BCL11A which regulate and suppression of the HbF production.^[36] The SPY101-Cas9, RNP complex complementary binds to the enhancer region of BCL11A at 58th position and starts the endonuclease activity^[40] to delete the 200bp of BCL11A^[41] and creates the DSB in DNA this was repaired by NHEJ or HDR pathway.^[40] The binding efficiency of transcription factor GATA 1 was reduced when the mutation results in the inhibition of BCL11A expression and increasing the level of HbF production.^[39]

Alternatively, the large deletion of Hereditary Persistence of Foetal Haemoglobin (HPFH) in HBB gene cause alteration or mutation in cis- regulatory element of HBG gene, the binding site for BCL11A transcriptional repressor it leads to no longer suppression of HbF because the deletion removes the DNA sequence where the repressor normally binds.^[37] This large deletion and mutation significantly increase the γ - globin production which highlights the CRISPR/Cas precise editing in treating SCD.^[41] Then the patient undergoes chemotherapy to eliminate the mutated haemoglobin and the edited cells are reintroduced in the patient's blood stream by Intravenous injection (IV). The edited cells are established in bone marrow and produce new blood stem which is called HbF expressing RBCs. This high level HbF production transport the oxygen freely to the tissue by releasing the block in small vessel caused by sickle RBCs flow.^[36]

Duchenne Muscular Dystrophy (DMD)

DMD is the harmful X- linked recessive disease caused by the mutation in DMD gene^[42] and one of the largest gene in human genome and represent 0.1% of human genome^[44] which is responsible for dystrophin protein production and it function as to stabilize the muscle cells during contraction.^[42] Dystrophin protein is formed by encoding 3685 amino acids in the DMD gene.^[43] This gene contains 79 exons codes for 4 domains that are Actin- binding amino terminal domain (ABD1), Central Rod Domain, Cytosine Rich Domain which is necessary for dystrophin maintenance and Carboxyl Terminal Domain^[43] forms the dystrophin complex when these domains interact with components of cytoskeleton.^[44] The DMD affects ~1 in 3500- 5000 male in worldwide and severity of this disease leads to life-threatening complication such as cardiomyopathy and respiratory failure^[42] which may also cause death of patients between the age of 18 & 30.^[44] Mutation caused in DMD gene may accelerate the exon deletion leads to the formation of premature stop codon, frame shift mutation and dysfunction of dystrophin protein by producing truncated form of protein.^[45] Most commonly affected exons are Exon 51, Exon 53, Exon 45, Exon 44, Exon 43 which manifesting the symptoms like muscle damage, wasting in pelvic area, inflammation, and the enlargement of calves in skeletal muscle may cause the premature death.^[42] There are some major treatments available for DMD that are prednisone and deflazacort reduce and manage the symptoms only but also cause some adverse effects that are weight gain, bone fragility and behavioural changes.^[42] The curative treatment to removal of mutated exons permanently on DMD gene was mediated by gene editing techniques especially CRISPR/Cas9 system which involved in exon deletion, exon skipping, Base editing and Prime editing.

Exon Deletion

The deletion of exon 45 to 55 treats ~60% of DMD patients who contains the exon mutation in this region. This was performed in human myoblasts, by using 2sgRNA to target these exons which leads to the deletion of about 336 kb at exon 45-55 resulting the restoration of reading frame and produce the functional dystrophin.^[45]

Exon Skipping

The exon skipping in RNA splicing process is beneficial in the treatment of 83% of DMD patients. In mice, deletion of exon 44 was created using SpCas9 and sgRNA at the edge of exon 45, which triggered the skipping of exon 45 but also caused exons 43 and 46 to ligate, forming the reading frame containing a hybrid exon.^[45,46]

Base Editing

This became one of the latest and advanced tools in CRISPR. Briefly, a Cas9 variant (nCas9 or dCas9) was combined with the deaminase enzyme, which induces the conversion of purine to pyrimidine and pyrimidine to purine (A:T to G:C and C:G to T:A) at the intended target. Base editing using cytidine deaminase was first found in the rat, and later adenosine deaminase.^[47] In a mouse model, the nonsense mutation in exon 20 was corrected using the adenosine deaminase, which changed a premature stop codon (TAG) to a glutamine codon (CAG), thereby restoring dystrophin protein. Yuan et al. demonstrated successful skipping of exon 50 in the induced pluripotent stem cells (iPSCs) of DMD patients who lacked exon 51.^[48]

Prime Editing

Prime editing has the capability to substitute any type of nucleotide. It was developed by fusing nCas9 with an engineered reverse transcriptase, combined with **prime editing guide RNA (pegRNA)**.^[49] The pegRNA contains the sequence complementary to the target site, a Cas9 binding site, a primer binding site, and a reverse transcription template. A nick is created on the DNA strand containing the PAM sequence when the pegRNA binds to the target site, after which reverse transcription synthesizes new 3' DNA bases carrying the desired modification. This sequence is then incorporated into the genome and repaired by the endogenous DNA repair pathway. Prime editing has been shown to restore dystrophin protein expression and reframe the open reading frame (ORF) by inserting two nucleotides downstream of exon 50 in **DMD patients** with an exon 51 deletion.^[50]

Cystic Fibrosis (CF)

Mutation in the **Cystic Fibrosis Transmembrane Conductance Regulator (CFTR)** gene, which is a 1480–amino-acid-long anion transporter^[51] located at 7q31.2 of chromosome 7, was discovered by Francis Collins and Lap-Chee Tsui's group in 1989.^[52] It causes the autosomal recessive disease called cystic fibrosis (CF). The function of the CFTR channel protein is to transport chloride and bicarbonate anions through mucus-producing cells, followed by water flow, which regulates mucus to remain thin.^[53] Mutation or dysfunction of the CFTR channel causes abnormal movement of fluid across epithelial cells, resulting in mucus viscosity.^[51] impaired anion secretion, increased sodium absorption, and airway surface dehydration.^[52]

Patients with CF have multiple organs affected, such as the lungs, sinuses, gastrointestinal tract, liver, pancreas, and vas deferens, which are involved in mucus and sweat production.^[52] It is most common in Northern European populations and affects ~70,000 individuals worldwide^[51] about 90% of mortality and morbidity are associated with lung obstruction or failure.^[54]

Mutations in the CFTR gene are divided into six classes

- **Class I** – defective protein,
- **Class II** – malformation of protein processing,
- **Class III** – abnormal protein regulation,
- **Class IV** – protein conduction defect,
- **Class V** – reduced protein synthesis,
- **Class VI** – enhanced protein turnover.

About 70% of cases are caused by **Class II F508del**^[53], a deletion of three bases coding for phenylalanine at position 508 in the nucleotide-binding domain. This leads to premature protein degradation due to misfolding.^[54]

The major treatment for CF is **pancreatic enzyme replacement** and **CFTR modulators** approved by the FDA.^[51] However, these treatments are expensive and time-consuming. Thus, **gene editing** is considered a curative therapy for CF, requiring expression of functional CFTR from the non-functional form.^[55]

The **CRISPR/Cas9 system** is one of the most advanced tools in gene editing to treat genetic

diseases by correcting mutations in blood or somatic cells.^[56] iPSCs isolated from CF patients can be edited by CRISPR/Cas9 and differentiated into airway epithelial cells *ex vivo*, providing an accurate way to correct the CFTR gene.^[56] CRISPR/Cas9 has been used to correct CFTR mutations via HDR without leaving editing marks, as demonstrated by Firth et al., which improved CFTR protein production and channel activity. However, the efficiency of NHEJ repair mediated by CRISPR is about 10 times higher than HDR.^[57,58]

Researchers have also isolated stem cells from CF patients' lungs, engineered them with CRISPR/Cas9 to restore CFTR function, and reintroduced them into stem-cell niches, the microenvironments for cell survival and growth.^[59] Delivery of RNP complexes and donor templates using Adeno-Associated Viral Vector Serotype 6 (AAV6) into airway basal stem cells and bronchial epithelial cells with F508del mutation resulted in ~30–50% CFTR gene restoration.^[55,58] Furthermore, **Geurts et al.** created a human intestinal organoid model for the F508del mutation to study CF disease function and applied prime editing to correct Δ F508, restoring channel function in organoids after two weeks of electroporation.^[60]

Application of CRISPR/Cas9 in Cancer treatment

Cancer is caused by a set of mutations occurring in the genome through epigenetic modifications, which lead to the activation of oncogenes and the deactivation of tumor suppressor genes. Genetic mutations in cancer-related genes drive disease progression and tumorigenesis. The rate of morbidity and mortality increases with the rapid rise of cancer, and about 20% of deaths in Europe are caused by cancer, while ~8.8 million deaths were estimated worldwide in 2015. Traditional and conventional treatments for cancer include chemotherapy, surgery, targeted biotherapy, and radiotherapy, which improve patient survival but also cause adverse effects. Therefore, the use of the CRISPR/Cas9 system as a curative treatment for cancer is being explored. It can be applied through strategies such as gene knockout, CAR-T cell therapy (to induce the immune system by autologous and allogeneic approaches), and by creating double-strand breaks (DSBs) at target mutational sites, resulting in tumor elimination and suppression of cell proliferation.^[61,62, 63, 64]

Lung Cancer

Lung cancer is often driven by mutations in the epidermal growth factor receptor (EGFR) and related oncogenic pathways.^[23] CRISPR/Cas9 has emerged as a therapeutic strategy to directly target these drivers through two main approaches.^[24] In the first, single-guide RNAs (sgRNAs) are designed against mutant EGFR sequences and form ribonucleoprotein (RNP)

complexes with Cas9. When delivered into lung cancer cells, the sgRNA–Cas9 complex cleaves the mutated EGFR loci, thereby disrupting oncogenic signaling.^[25] The second approach uses ex vivo editing of patient-derived T cells. Here, CRISPR/Cas9 disrupts the PD-1 gene, enhancing T cell–mediated tumor killing after reinfusion.^[26]

Clinical studies demonstrate the feasibility of these strategies. For example, Cheng et al. showed that lentiviral delivery of CRISPR/Cas9 targeting the L858R EGFR mutation disrupted the MYC oncogene, reducing lung cancer cell proliferation.^[27] Similarly, vector-based sgRNA–Cas9 complexes corrected β -catenin mutations in murine models, with systemic delivery via tail vein injection significantly suppressing tumor progression.^[28]

Breast Cancer

Breast cancer (BC) is the most frequently diagnosed cancer in women, with 2.1 million new cases reported worldwide in 2018.^[29] Current treatments such as tamoxifen and aromatase inhibitors act on hormone receptors, but many patients eventually develop resistance. Another major driver is HER2 amplification. CRISPR/Cas9 targeting of HER2 exons 5, 10, and 12 has been shown to suppress proliferation and tumor progression.^[30] Inactivation of lipocalin-2 and genes linked to triple-negative breast cancer (TNBC) reduced epithelial-to-mesenchymal transition in vitro, thereby weakening tumorigenic potential.^[31] Restoration of the TP53 414delC mutation in PC3 cells also increased apoptosis, highlighting TP53 as a key therapeutic target.^[32] Collectively, these findings underscore the potential of CRISPR/Cas9 editing to overcome resistance and oncogenic drivers in breast cancer.

Liver Cancer

Hepatocellular carcinoma (HCC) is the most frequent type of primary liver cancer with high tendency to be revealed at an advanced stage, along with aggressive growth pattern. Among some of the most significant molecular pathways that have been identified as having a role to play in the development of HCC is that of TRAF3 (TNF Receptor-Associated Factor 3), PTEN (Phosphatase and Tensin Homolog), and CTNNB1 (Catenin Beta 1). The efficiency of the mediation of these targets by CRISPR/Cas9 has demonstrated potent anticancer effects. Loss of TRAF3 potentiates NF- κ B signaling leading to tumor expansion and CRISPR/Cas9 ablation of TRAF3 reverses NF- κ B signals and suppresses tumor vascularization.^[70] Equally, the loss of PTEN leads to the impairment of the PI3K/AKT pathway and ineffective restraint of cell growth, whereas PTEN reinstatement using the CRISPR technique is able to mitigate the pathway, cause apoptosis, and inhibit tumor

growth.^[64] In addition, CRISPR-based CRISPR knockout of CTNNB1 is sufficient to shut down the Wnt/beta-catenin pathway, resulting in decreased proliferation, increased apoptosis and suppression of tumor growth.^[70] Genomic instability related to another commonly occurring mutation in HCC, that of TP53, favors malignant transformation. The use of TP53 sgRNAs to deliver Cas9 nuclease to mutations of TP53 has been reported to restore partial TP53 function, inhibit cell proliferation and introduce apoptosis in cancer cells.^[71] Together these data emphasize the potential of CRISPR/Cas9 as a therapeutic agent against hepatocellular carcinoma oncogenic drivers.

CONCLUSION

First discovered as an adaptive immune mechanism in bacteria, the CRISPR/Cas9 technology has become one of the most readily adaptable genome editing technologies of the modern age. The impact of this system in molecular biology can be illustrated by the historical development of this marvelous discovery - the discovery of clustered repeats in *E. coli* to the programmable genome cleavage which was later rewarded with a Nobel Prize. Mechanistically, the CRISPR/Cas9 mechanism is the ability to cut DNA at a specified position and then utilize the intracellular repair process non-homologous end joining (NHEJ) and homology-directed repair (HDR).

The ease of guide RNA design added to the efficiency of Cas9-mediated cleavage has made this system a core concept behind numerous applications, such as functional genomics, disease modeling (breast cancer modeling, neurodegenerative diseases, and cardiovascular disease modeling), and gene therapy. The clinical progress in recent years, such as the food approval of CASGEVY to treat sickle cell disease and beta-thalassemia, is an indication of significant therapy potential. Nevertheless, major obstacles next remain, most notably, in the field of off-target effects, immunogenicity of Cas nucleases, and the precise delivery of editing machinery to target cells.

Further studies are thus anticipated to encompass the improvement of Cas9 variants that can increase specificity, increase optimization of truncated sgRNAs or chemically modified sgRNAs, and develop new methods of delivery, including lipid nanoparticles and viral vectors. Overcoming such constraints will be critical to the realization of the clinical potential of CRISPR/Cas9 and their safe translation to future therapies.

REFERENCES

1. Mengstie, M. A., & Wondimu, B. Z. Mechanism and applications of CRISPR/Cas- 9-mediated genome editing. *Biologics: Targets and Therapy*, 2021; 15: 353–361. <https://doi.org/10.2147/BTT.S326902>.
2. Ishino, Y., Shinagawa, H., Makino, K., Amemura, M., & Nakata, A. Nucleotide sequence of the *iap* gene, responsible for alkaline phosphatase isozyme conversion in *Escherichia coli*, and identification of the gene product. *Journal of Bacteriology*, 1987; 169(12): 5429–5433. <https://doi.org/10.1128/jb.169.12.5429-5433.1987>.
3. Zhang, H., Qin, C., An, C. et al. Application of the CRISPR/Cas9- based gene editing technique in basic research, diagnosis, and therapy of cancer. *Mol. Cancer*, 2021; 20: 126. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12943-021-01431-6>.
4. Jiang, H., Tang, M., Xu, Z., Wang, Y., Li, M., Zheng, S., Zhu, J., Lin, Z., & Zhang, M. CRISPR/Cas9 system and its applications in nervous system diseases. *Genes & Diseases*, 2024; 11(1): 675–686. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.gendis.2023.03.017>.
5. Barrangou, R., & Marraffini, L. A. CRISPR–Cas systems: Prokaryotes upgrade to adaptive immunity. *Molecular Cell*, 2014; 54(2): 234–244. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.molcel.2014.03.011>.
6. Gostimskaya, I. CRISPR–Cas9: A history of its discovery and ethical considerations of its use in genome editing. *Biochemistry (Moscow)*, 2022; 87(8): 777–788. <https://doi.org/10.1134/S0006297922080090>.
7. Bolotin, A., Quinquis, B., Sorokin, A., & Ehrlich, S. D. Clustered regularly interspaced short palindrome repeats (CRISPRs) have spacers of extrachromosomal origin. *Microbiology*, 2005; 151(8): 2551–2561. <https://doi.org/10.1099/mic.0.28048-0>.
8. Elliott, J. F. K., McLeod, D. V., Taylor, T. B., Westra, E. R., Gandon, S., & Watson, B. N. J. Conditions for the spread of CRISPR-Cas immune systems into bacterial populations. *The ISME Journal*, 2024; 18(1): wræ108. <https://doi.org/10.1093/ismejo/wrae108>.
9. Rodriguez- Rodriguez, D.R., Ramirez-Solis, R., Garza-Elizondo, M.A., Garza- Rodriguez, M.L., and Barrera-Saldana, H.A. Genome editing: A perspective on the application of CRISPR/Cas9 to study human diseases (Review). *International Journal of Molecular Medicine*, 2019; 43(3): 1559-1574. <https://doi.org/10.3892/ijmm.2019.4112>.
10. Pacesa, M., Pelae, O., & Jinek, M. Past, present, and future of CRISPR genome editing technologies. *Cell*, 2024; 187(3): 1076–1096. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cell.2024.01.042>.
11. Xu, Y., & Li, Z. CRISPR-Cas systems: Overview, innovations and applications in human disease research and gene therapy. *Computational and Structural Biotechnology Journal*,

- 2020; 18: 2401–2415. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.csbj.2020.08.031>.
12. Newsom, S., Parameshwaran, H. P., Martin, L., & Rajan, R. The CRISPR-Cas Mechanism for Adaptive Immunity and Alternate Bacterial Functions Fuels Diverse Biotechnologies. *Frontiers in Cellular and Infection Microbiology*, 2021; 10: Article 619763. <https://www.frontiersin.org/articles/10.3389/fcimb.2020.619763/full>.
 13. Koonin, E. V., Makarova, K. S., & Zhang, F. Diversity, classification and evolution of CRISPR-Cas systems. *Current Opinion in Microbiology*, 2017; 37: 67–78. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.mib.2017.05.008>.
 14. Pyzocha, N. K., & Chen, S. Diverse Class 2 CRISPR-Cas effector proteins for genome engineering applications. *ACS Chemical Biology*, 2018; 13(2): 347-356. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acscchembio.7b00800>.
 15. Zheng, Y., Li, Y., Zhou, K., Li, T., Van Dusen, N, J., & Hua, Y. Precise genome- editing in human diseases: mechanisms, strategies and applications. *Signal Transduction and Targeted Therapy*, 2024; 9(47). <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41392-024-01750-2>.
 16. Becker, S., Boch, J. TALE and TALEN genome editing technologies. *Gene and genome editing* 2021; 2: 100007. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ggedit.2021.100007>.
 17. Shao, M., Xu, T. R., & Chen, C. S. The big bang of genome editing technology: development and application of the CRISPR/Cas9 system in disease animal models. *Zoological Research*, 2016; 37(4): 191–204. <https://doi.org/10.13918/j.issn.2095-8137.2016.4.191>.
 18. Ceasar, S. A., Rajan, V., Prykhozhiy, S. V., Berman, J. N., & Ignacimuthu, S. Insert, remove or replace: A highly advanced genome editing system using CRISPR/Cas9. *Biochimica et Biophysica Acta (BBA)-* 2016; 1863(1): 2333–2344. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.bbamcr.2016.06.009>.
 19. Zhu, Y. (2022). Advances in CRISPR/Cas9. *BioMed Research International*, 2022; Article 9978571. <https://doi.org/10.1155/2022/9978571>.
 20. Ruhn, A. L., Escalera-Maurer, A., Bratovic, M., & Charpentier, E. CRISPR-Cas in *Streptococcus pyogenes*. *RNA Biology*, 2019; 16(4): 380–389. <https://doi.org/10.1080/15476286.2019.1582974>.
 21. Hille, F., & Charpentier, E. CRISPR-Cas: biology, mechanisms and relevance. *Philosophical Transactions of the Royal Society B: Biological Sciences*, 2016; 371: 20150496. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1098/rstb.2015.0496>.
 22. Ishino, Y., Krupovic, M., & Forterre, P. History of CRISPR-Cas from encounter with a mysterious repeated sequence to genome editing technology. *Journal of Bacteriology*,

- 2018; 200(7): e00580-17. <https://doi.org/10.1128/JB.00580-17>.
23. Jiang, F., Doudna, J.A. CRISPR-Cas9 structures and mechanisms. *Annu. Rev. Biophys.* 2017; 46(1): 505-529. <https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev-biophys-062215-010822>.
24. Mushtaq, M., Ahmad Dar, A., Skalicky, M., Tyagi, A., Bhagat, N., Basu, U., Bhat, B.A., Zaid, A., Ali, S., Dar, T.-U.-H., et al. CRISPR-Based Genome Editing Tools: Insights into Technological Breakthroughs and Future Challenges. *Genes*, 2021; 12(797). <https://doi.org/10.3390/genes12060797>.
25. Rasheed, A., Gili, R. A., Hassan, M. U., Mahmood, A., Qari, S., Zaman, Q.U., Ilyas, M., Aamer, M., Batool, M., Li, H., et al. A Critical Review: Recent Advancements in the Use of CRISPR/Cas9 Technology to Enhance Crops and Alleviate Global Food Crises. *Current Issues in Molecular Biology*, 2021; 43: 1950-1976. <https://doi.org/10.3390/cimb43030135>.
26. Rahimi, S., Balusamy, S. R., Perumalsamy, H., Ståhlberg, A., & Mijaković, I. CRISPR-Cas target recognition for sensing viral and cancer biomarkers. *Nucleic Acid Research*, 2024; 52: 10040-10067. <https://doi.org/10.1093/nar/gkae736>.
27. Gaj, T. G., Sirk, S. J., Shui, S.-L., & Liu, J. *Genome-Editing Technologies: Principles and Applications*. Cold Spring Harbor Perspectives in Biology, 2016; 8(a023754). <https://doi.org/10.1101/cshperspect.a023754>.
28. Zhang, R., Xu, W., Shao, S., & Wang, Q. Gene Silencing Through CRISPR Interference in Bacteria: Current Advances and Future Prospects. *Frontiers in Microbiology*, 2021; 12: Article 635227. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fmicb.2021.635227>.
29. Liao, H., Wu, J., VanDusen, N.J., Li, Y., & Zheng, Y. CRISPR–Cas9-mediated homology-directed repair for precise gene editing. *Molecular Therapy. Nucleic Acids*, 2024; 35: 102344. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.omtn.2024.102344>.
30. Yang, H., Ren, S., Yu, S., Pan, H., Li, T., Ge, S., Zhang, J., & Xia, N. Methods Favoring Homology-Directed Repair Choice in Response to CRISPR/Cas9 Induced- Double Strand Breaks. *International Journal of Molecular Sciences*, 2020; 21: 6461. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijms21186461>.
31. Pannunzio, N.R., Watanabe, G., & Lieber, M. R. Nonhomologous DNA end- joining for repair of DNA double-strand breaks. *The Journal of Biological Chemistry*, 2018; 293(27): 10512–10523. <https://doi.org/10.1074/jbc.TM117.000374>.
32. Elendu, C., Amaechi, D.C., Alakwe- Ojimba, C.E., Elendu, T. C., Elendu, R. C., Ayabazu, C. P., Aina, T. O., Aborisade, O., & Adenikinju, J.S. Understanding Sickle Cell Disease: Causes, Symptoms, and Treatment Options. *Medicine*, 2023; 102(38): e35237.

- <http://dx.doi.org/10.1097/MD.00000000000035237>.
33. Singh, A., Irfan, H., Fatima, E., Nazir, Z., Verma, A., & Akilimali, A. Revolutionary breakthrough: FDA approves CASGEVY, the first CRISPR/Cas9 gene therapy for sickle cell disease. *Annals of Medicine & Surgery*, 2024; 86: 4555-4559. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1097/MS9.00000000000002146>.
34. Parums, D. V. Editorial: First Regulatory Approvals for CRISPR–Cas9 Therapeutic Gene Editing for Sickle Cell Disease and Transfusion-Dependent β -Thalassemia. *Medical Science Monitor*, 2024; 30: e944204. <https://doi.org/10.12659/MSM.944204>.
35. Tariq, H., Khurshid, F., Khan, M. H., Dilshad, A., Zain, A., Rasool, W., Jawaid, A., Kunwar, D., Khanduja, S. N., & Akbar, A. CRISPR/Cas9 in the treatment of sickle cell disease (SCD) and its comparison with traditional treatment approaches: a review. *Annals of Medicine & Surgery*, 2024; 86: 5938–5946. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1097/MS9.00000000000002478>.
36. Cetin, B., Erendor, F., Eksi, Y. E., Sanlioglu, A. D., & Sanlioglu, S. Advancing CRISPR genome editing into gene therapy clinical trials: Progress and future prospects. *Expert Reviews in Molecular Medicine*, 2025; 27(e16): 1–33. <https://doi.org/10.1017/erm.2025.10>.
37. Zarghamian, P., Klermund, J., & Cathomen, T. Clinical genome editing to treat sickle cell disease—A brief update. *Frontiers in Medicine*, 2023; 9: 1065377. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fmed.2022.1065377>.
38. Park, S. H., & Bao, G. CRISPR/Cas9 gene editing for curing sickle cell disease. *Transfusion Apheresis Science*, 2021; 60(1): 103060. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.transci.2021.103060>.
39. Kerwash, E., Sajic, M., Rantell, K.R., McBlane, J.W., Johnston, J. D., Niewiarowska, A., & Butler, A.S., Cole, S. Regulatory Assessment of Casgevy for the Treatment of Transfusion-Dependent β -Thalassemia and Sickle Cell Disease with Recurrent Vaso-Occlusive Crises. *Current Issues in Molecular Biology*, 2024; 46: 8209–8225. <https://doi.org/10.3390/cimb46080485>.
40. Laurent, M., Geoffroy, G., Pavani, G., & Guiraud, S. CRISPR-Based Gene Therapies: From Preclinical to Clinical Treatments. *Cells*, 2024; 13: 800. <https://doi.org/10.3390/cells13100800>.
41. Sun, J., Wang, J., Zheng, D., & Hu, X. Advances in therapeutic application of CRISPR-Cas9. *Briefings in Functional Genomics*, 2020; 19(3): 164–174.

- <https://doi.org/10.1093/bfpg/elz031>.
42. Ali, A., Rahman, M. Y., & Sheikh, D. The Role of CRISPR/Cas9 in Revolutionizing Duchenne's Muscular Dystrophy Treatment: Opportunities and Obstacles. *Glob Med Genet*, 2024; 11: 349–357. <https://doi.org/10.1055/s-0044-1791803>.
 43. Krishna, L., Prashant, A., Kumar, Y.H., Paneyala, S., Patil, S.J., Ramachandra, S.C., Vishwanath, P. Molecular and Biochemical Therapeutic Strategies for Duchenne Muscular Dystrophy. *Neurol. Int.*, 2024; 16: 731–760. <https://doi.org/10.3390/neurolint16040055>.
 44. Mbakam, C. H., Lamothe, G., Tremblay, G., & Tremblay, J. P. CRISPR-Cas9 Gene Therapy for Duchenne Muscular Dystrophy. *Neurotherapeutics*, 2022; 19: 931–941. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13311-022-01197-9>.
 45. Choi, E., & Koo, T. CRISPR technologies for the treatment of Duchenne muscular dystrophy. *Molecular Therapy*, 2021; 29(11): 3179-3188. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ymthe.2021.04.002>.
 46. Mbakam, C. H., Lamothe, G., & Tremblay, J. P. Therapeutic Strategies for Dystrophin Replacement in Duchenne Muscular Dystrophy. *Frontiers in Medicine*, 2022; 9: 859930. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fmed.2022.859930>.
 47. Hanson, B., Wood, M. J., & Roberts, T. C. Molecular correction of Duchenne muscular dystrophy by splice modulation and gene editing. *RNA Biology*, 2021; 18(7): 1048-1062. <https://doi.org/10.1080/15476286.2021.1874161>.
 48. Erkut, E., & Yokota, T. (CRISPR Therapeutics for Duchenne Muscular Dystrophy. *International Journal of Molecular Sciences*, 2022; 23: 1832. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijms23031832>.
 49. Chemello, F., Olson, E.N., & Bassel-Duby, R. CRISPR-Editing Therapy for Duchenne Muscular Dystrophy. *Human Gene Therapy*, 2023; 34(9-10). <https://doi.org/10.1089/hum.2023.053>.
 50. Chen, G., Wei, T., Yang, H., Li, G., Feng, & Li, H. CRISPR-Based Therapeutic Editing for Duchenne Muscular Dystrophy: Advances, Challenges and Perspectives. *Cells*, 2022; 11: 2964. <https://doi.org/10.3390/cells11192964>.
 51. Hodges, C. A., & Conlon, R. A. Delivering on the promise of gene editing for cystic fibrosis. *Genes & Diseases*, 2019; 6: 97–108. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.gendis.2018.11.005>.
 52. Wang, G. Genome Editing for Cystic Fibrosis. *Cells*, 2023; 12: 1555. <https://doi.org/10.3390/cells12121555>.
 53. Rafeeq, M.M., & Murad, H. A. Cystic fibrosis: current therapeutic targets and future

- approaches. *Journal of Translational Medicine*, 2017; 15(1): 84. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12967-017-1133-9>.
54. Kotagama, O. W., Jayasinghe, C. D., & Abeysinghe, T. Era of Genomic Medicine: A Narrative Review on CRISPR Technology as a Potential Therapeutic Tool for Human Diseases. *BioMed Research International*, Article ID, 2019; 1369682. <https://doi.org/10.1155/2019/1369682>.
55. da Silva Sanchez, A., Paunovska, K., Cristian, A., & Dahlman, J. E. Treating Cystic Fibrosis with mRNA and CRISPR. *Human Gene Therapy*, 2020; 31(17-18): 940–947. <https://doi.org/10.1089/hum.2020.137>.
56. Kang, K., Song, Y., Kim, I., & Kim, T.- J. Therapeutic Applications of the CRISPR-Cas System. *Bio engineering*, 2022; 9: 477. <https://doi.org/10.3390/bioengineering9090477>.
57. Pranke, I., Golec, A., Hinzpeter, A., Edelman, A., & Sermet-Gaudelus, I. Emerging Therapeutic Approaches for Cystic Fibrosis. From Gene Editing to Personalized Medicine. *Frontiers in Pharmacology*, 2019; 10: 121. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fphar.2019.00121>.
58. Ensink, M., Mottais, A., Detry, C., Leal, T., & Carlon, M. S. On the Corner of Models and Cure: Gene Editing in Cystic Fibrosis. *Frontiers in Pharmacology*, 2021; 12: Article 662110. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fphar.2021.662110>.
59. Maranghi, M., & Pistrutto, G. Innovative Therapeutic Strategies for Cystic Fibrosis: Moving Forward to CRISPR Technique. *Frontiers in Pharmacology*, 2018; 9: 396. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fphar.2018.00396>.
60. Godbout, K., & Tremblay, J. P. Prime Editing for Human Gene Therapy: Where Are We Now? *Cells*, 2023; 12: 536. <https://doi.org/10.3390/cells12040536>.
61. Ding, S., Liu, J., Han, X., & Tang, M. CRISPR/Cas9-Mediated Gene Editing in Cancer Therapy. *International Journal of Molecular Sciences*, 2023; 24: 16325. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijms242216325>.
62. Song, Z., Tao, Y., Liu, Y., & Li, J. Advances in delivery systems for CRISPR/Cas-mediated cancer treatment: a focus on viral vectors and extracellular vesicles. *Frontiers in Immunology*, 2024; 15: 1444437. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fimmu.2024.1444437>.
63. Rabaan, A.A., AlSaihati, H., Bukhamsin, R., Bakhrebah, M.A., Nassar, M.S., Alsaleh, A.A., Alhashem, Y.N., Bukhamseen, A.Y., Al-Ruhimy, K., Alotaibi, M., et al. Application of CRISPR/Cas9 Technology in Cancer Treatment: A Future Direction. *Curr. Oncol.* 2023; 30: 1954-1976. <https://doi.org/10.3390/currenol30020152>.
64. Ratan, Z. A., Son, Y. - J., Haidere, M. F., Uddin, B.M.M., Yusuf, A., Zaman, S.B., Kim,

- J.- H., Anjuman Banu, L., & Cho, J.Y. CRISPR-Cas9: a promising genetic engineering approach in cancer research. *Therapeutic Advances in Medical Oncology*, 2018; 10(1-15). <https://doi.org/10.1177/1758834018755089>.
65. Tiruneh G/Medhin, M., Chekol Abebe, E., Sisay, T., Berhane, N., Snr, B. T., & Dejenie, T.A. Current Applications and Future Perspectives of CRISPR-Cas9 for the Treatment of Lung Cancer. *Biologics: Targets and Therapy*, 2021; 15: 199–204. <https://doi.org/10.2147/BTT.S322712>.
66. Hazafa, A., Mumtaz, M., Farooq, M. F., Bilal, S., Chaudhry, S. N., Firdous, M., Naeem, H., Ullah, M. O., Yameen, M., Mukhtiar, M.S., & Zafar, F. CRISPR/Cas9: A powerful genome editing technique for the treatment of cancer cells with present challenges and future directions. *Life Sciences*, 2020; 263: 118525. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.lfs.2020.118525>.
67. Ahmed Khan, F., Pandupuspitasari, N. S., Chun-Jie, H., Ao, Z., Jamal, M., Zohaib, A., Khan, F. A., Raihana Hakim, M., & Shujun, Z. CRISPR/Cas9 therapeutics: A cure for cancer and other genetic diseases. *Oncotarget*, 2017; 7(32): 52541–52541. <https://doi.org/10.18632/oncotarget.v7i32>.
68. Ahmed, M., Daoud, G. H., Mohamed, A., & Harati, R. New insights into the therapeutic applications of CRISPR/Cas9 genome editing in breast cancer. *Genes*, 2021; 12: 723. <https://doi.org/10.3390/genes12050723>.
69. Padayachee, J., & Singh, M. Therapeutic applications of CRISPR/Cas9 in breast cancer and delivery potential of gold nanomaterials. *Nanobiomedicine*, 2020; 7(1-15). <https://doi.org/10.1177/1849543520983196>.
70. Amjad, E., Pezzani, R., & Sokouti, B. A review on the literature on the use of CRISPR/Cas9 gene therapy to treat hepatocellular carcinoma. *Oncology Research*, 2024; 32(3): 439–461. <https://doi.org/10.32604/or.2023.044473>.
71. Lv, W., Li, T., Wang, S., Wang, H., Li, X., Zhang, S., Wang, L., Xu, Y., & Wei, W. The Application of the CRISPR/Cas9 System in the Treatment of Hepatitis B Liver Cancer. *Technology in Cancer Research & Treatment*, 2021; 20(1-11). <https://doi.org/10.1177/15330338211045206>.